

PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPING THE " GREEN ECONOMY" IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya: O 'zbekiston Respublikasi iqtisodiyotining barqaror o 'sishini ta 'minlash va ekologik muammolarni yengillashtirish maqsadida yashil iqtisodiyot tamoyillarini joriy etish zarur. Yashil iqtisodiyot- resurslarni samarali boshqarish, atrof muhitni muhofaza qilish va qayta tiklanadigan Kelgusida, yashil iqtisodiyot tamoyillarini keng joriy etish natijasida , va xalq farovonligini oshishi kutilmoqda.

Аннотация: Для обеспечения устойчивого роста экономики Республики Узбекистан и смягчения экологических проблем необходимо внедрение принципов «зеленой экономики». Зеленая экономика — это система эффективного управления ресурсами, охраны окружающей среды и возобновляемой энергии. В будущем в результате повсеместного внедрения принципов зеленой экономики ожидается рост благосостояния народа.

Abstract: In order to ensure sustainable growth of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and alleviate environmental problems, it is necessary to introduce the principles of "green economy". Green economy is a system of efficient resource management, environmental protection and renewable energy. In the future, as a result of the widespread introduction of the principles of green economy, it is expected that the well-being of the people will increase.

Kalit so 'zlar: Barqaror rivojlanish, orolbo 'yi mintaqasini tiklash, ekologik innovatsiyalar, iqlim o 'zgarishi, qishloq xo 'jaligida ekologik texnologiyalar, ifloslanishini kamaytirish, ekologiya va toza transport tizimi.

Ключевые слова: Устойчивое развитие, восстановление региона Аральского моря, экологические инновации, изменение климата, экологические технологии в сельском хозяйстве, снижение загрязнения, экология и чистая транспортная система.

Keywords: Sustainable development, restoration of the Aral Sea region, ecological innovations, climate change, ecological technologies in agriculture, pollution reduction, ecology and clean transport system.

Introduction. Currently, Uzbekistan, while continuing its rapid economic development, pays special attention to sustainable and environmentally friendly development. Although the country is rich in natural resources, their effective and economical use is important for environmental protection and ensuring socio-economic stability in the future[1]. Therefore, Uzbekistan is choosing a sustainable development path based on the concept of a green economy. The concept of a green economy is important for ensuring economic development on the basis of environmental safety and rational use of natural resources. For this reason, Uzbekistan is choosing a sustainable development path based on the concept of a green economy. The concept of a green economy implies ensuring economic development on the basis of environmental safety and rational use of natural resources.[2] This is especially important for the quality of life of the country's population and environmental protection, especially with the use of the economy in the agricultural, energy, industrial and transport sectors. Uzbekistan is a country with a potential for renewable energy sources such as solar energy and wind. The transition to renewable energy in the energy sector can be economically beneficial, on the one hand. Our country plans to obtain 25% of its electricity from renewable sources by 2030. Another key area is the effective management of water resources. Water conservation, modernization of irrigation systems and water recycling are important issues for Uzbekistan.

From the perspective of a green economy, the introduction of modern and environmentally friendly methods of water use will help to reduce water scarcity and increase agricultural productivity in the future. And a number of projects in Uzbekistan in the field of waste recycling and the implementation of zero-waste technologies will not only help reduce waste, but also bring additional income to the economy through recycling. In order to reduce harmful emissions from transport, Uzbekistan aims to develop electric vehicles and introduce environmentally friendly fuels. New projects are being implemented in this area on the basis of national programs and international cooperation. Uzbekistan is expanding cooperation with international financial organizations and developed countries to develop a green economy.

In particular, there are agreements with international organizations such as the UN, the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank on financing environmental projects and providing technical assistance. This cooperation is an important factor in the transition to a green economy. Problems such as climate change, environmental pollution and natural resource scarcity around the world increase the need to develop a green economy. The green economy is important for the following reasons: Reducing climate change - a green economy helps reduce emissions and achieve carbon neutrality, Conserving natural resources - natural resources are preserved in the long term through the use of renewable resources, Improving social welfare - the

introduction of green technologies creates new jobs and helps to raise environmental awareness of the population. Agriculture

As one of the main sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan, the introduction of green economy principles will have a positive impact on this sector. Key measures: widespread introduction of water-saving technologies, namely drip irrigation systems, which allow for the efficient use of water resources. Development of organic agriculture to produce environmentally friendly products by reducing the use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers. Agroforestry (organic agricultural system) - planting trees on cultivated areas to prevent deforestation. The development of a waste management system in our country is one of the important areas of the green economy. The government aims to increase the level of waste recycling to 40% by 2025. The main areas of these are: Reduction of plastic waste - Phase out single-use plastic products. Development of recycling enterprises. Increase the number of waste recycling plants by attracting local and foreign investors. [4]

Conducting public awareness campaigns on waste separation and recycling. In particular, the transport sector is one of the main factors of air pollution in Uzbekistan. Therefore, it is necessary to develop green transport technologies. Encourage the use of electric vehicles by subsidizing the purchase of electric vehicles by the state and providing them with tax benefits. Modernizing public transport - expanding the metropolitan system of electric buses. Increasing bicycle and pedestrian paths to promote the use of environmentally friendly means of transport in cities. Problems in the development of a green economy and ways to solve them.

The main problems are that the development of a green economy requires significant investment. A large amount of money is needed to introduce renewable energy sources, develop environmentally friendly technologies, and create infrastructure for waste processing. Many enterprises do not have sufficient financial resources for environmental projects. The production and use of environmentally friendly technologies in Uzbekistan has not yet become widespread. Local enterprises do not have sufficient access to energy-efficient technologies and waste processing equipment. Many citizens still do not pay enough attention to issues such as the use of environmentally friendly products, waste sorting, and water and energy conservation.

The active participation of citizens in the process of transition to a green economy is considered important. One of the largest environmental problems in the Central Asian region is the focus of attention of ecologists around the world. In the middle of the 20th century, it was one of the largest lakes in the world. The Aral Sea has now almost disappeared. This phenomenon is the result of human activity and natural factors, and its consequences have a significant impact on the ecological, social and economic spheres. Hundreds of thousands of tons of salt and dust from the dried-up bottom of the Aral Sea are being released into the air, spreading not only over

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Uzbekistan, but also throughout Central Asia and other regions. This reduces soil fertility and makes the area unsuitable for living. [8]

The salt and dust released into the air as a result of the island's construction contain harmful substances. This causes respiratory diseases, allergies and other health problems. Due to the crisis in agriculture, fishing and other industries in the region, many people have lost their jobs and have been forced to leave the region.

In conclusion, it can be said that today the most important aspect and at the same time the most difficult stage in the development of the Digital Economy is to simplify the business environment and minimize the costs of interacting with the state by people and businesses.

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